

THE DIFFERENCES BETWEEN OLD AND MODERN METHODS OF TEACHING ENGLISH IN PRIMARY SCHOOLS

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Annotation: *This article discusses old and modern methods used to improve students' knowledge of English in primary education.*

Key words: *method, old method, new method*

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматриваются старые и современные методы, применяемые для совершенствования знаний учащихся начальных классов по английскому языку.

Ключевые слова: *метод, старый метод, новый метод*

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqolada boshlang'ich sinflarda ingliz tili fani bo'yicha o'quvchilarning bilim darajasini oshirishda qo'llanadigan eski hamda zamonaviy metodlar haqida so'z boradi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *metod, eski metod, yangi metod*

Nowadays, perfect knowledge of foreign languages is very important for our country which is striving to take a worthy place in the world community and actively working in all specialties, especially in business, science, culture, politics and economics, that can be the foundation for its great future. Actually, one of the decisions that led to positive changes in primary education was the resolution of the first president of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December the 10th, 2012 № PQ-1875 'On further improvement of the system of learning foreign languages'. In accordance with this resolution, in order to increase the interest of foreign languages, especially English from the primary classes to teach English lessons in all secondary schools from the first grade in a variety of fun and playful ways as well as to develop students' oral speeches. From the beginning of the second grade the transition to modern methods of teaching the alphabet, reading and writing is carried out gradually.

The education system has been improving over the years. The resolution of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev №. PQ-5117 of May the 19th, 2021 'On measures to bring the promotion of foreign language learning in the Republic of Uzbekistan to a qualitatively new level' clearly demonstrates the importance of foreign languages in our country. The head of our state also supports the gradual transition to a new system of teaching foreign languages. The reason for this is the 21st century – 'Age of science and technology'. Therefore, the world is highly accelerating at the same time as science and technology. We have to be knowledgeable to keep up with the today's quick life-cycle. The future of the government is in the hands of the youths. As long as the younger generation is educated, the state will develop. Science should also be taught from the young ages. Because 'Knowledge which is acquired in childhood is like a pattern carved on a stone'. In order for children to spend their time meaningfully, they must participate in various science clubs. President Shavkat Mirziyoyev says: 'A child's leisure time is the enemy's work time'. This is why the child won't do useless actions and won't be a bad person when they spend the time for good things. The system of teaching English in primary schools also increases a child's interests in a foreign language from an early age.

In a few years the introduction of teaching system of English in primary schools, some teaching methods and the development of sufficient skills in students seem to be outdated. Because there are several differences in the process of teaching foreign languages when it comes to high school students and younger students. I think it will be more useful to teach a foreign language in a special way according to their level than outdated methods.

If we talk about such old methods, first of all it is necessary to dwell on the environment of lesson plan. In such cases, we see that foreign language teachers use their mother tongue more when they are teaching. It is true that sometimes young learners may be given difficult or confusing topics and assignments, but in most cases I think it is possible to explain the topic to students through a variety of behaviors: body languages or visual aids.

Usual approaches of teaching are old versions in which teachers are the controller of the learners where they teach and take the perfect responsibility of the acquiring aura. All the duties and powers are officially given to the teacher and they, being the controller in the class, play the role of an instructor for the students and also the decision maker for receiving the choices of what to teach and how to teach.

Classroom, a word that means a setting where an instructor stands in front of a class of 25 to 30 students and more, delivering a lecture with a specific gravity, ups and downs in their voice. This is the style of teaching that was prevalent when we were in school, such as, two decades ago. However, teaching approaches changed over the years, and though it was one of the most effective methods of teaching English to young students, it no longer considered the same now. This is due to various reasons, maybe because:

- The present generation gets exposure to the world through social media
- Their knowledge base is augmenting by the information available on
- The internet (as long as you surf it for good purposes)
- The students nowadays are more impatient and to grab their attention, teaching methods need to cater for their dynamic
- Thinking process.

According to Asher and James (1982), 'Methods are the combination of techniques that are used and made flexible by the teachers in the classrooms to teach their students and approaches are the philosophies of teachers about language teaching that can be applied in the classrooms by using different ways of language teaching'.

Now, we recommend you, dear readers, to try on the following methods in your teaching:

- **TPR** (Total Physical Response). This method involves acting out language rather than speaking. It can be through mimicry or only responding to audiovisual cues. Games like '**Simon says...**' or the charades are classic examples of this method of teaching. This method is a fun way of learning language and therefore is very useful.

- **Audio-lingual Method.** This method of teaching English was initially called 'the Army Method,' as it was devised during the Second World War when it became necessary for soldiers to learn the language of their opponents. It resembles a direct method in a way. This approach is based on thinking in the language and expressing thoughts in the same. And in the process, learning happens.

To cut it short, teachers are the torch bearers of a civilized society. For ages, teachers have used different methods, approaches, and styles to suit the child's requirements. Teaching English as a second language is a challenge as we can see that for non-native speakers, various methods need to be devised. In India, English teaching is an exciting task, as we are multi-lingual and have a diverse socio-economic background. Still, general thinking identifies the English language as a

mark of being literate. So teachers of this century put together all the methods to find the best one for our country. Although too much use of visual aids and gamification of education are still not widespread in our country.

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